

Explainable Machine Learning for prediction and monitoring of compressive strength in LC3 production

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Abstract. In this work, we leverage Machine Learning to accurately predict the 28-day compressive strength of co-grinded limestone-calcined-clay cement (LC3) in a production environment. We illustrate how ad-hoc measurements of chemical composition and particle size, including x-ray fluorescence, sieve analyses, Blaine and water demand, can be used for 28-day strength prediction. Our model reduces the prediction error by 30% compared to a baseline without Machine Learning. To obtain actionable insights and identify optimization potential, we apply techniques of eXplainable Artificial Intelligence and model interpretability. For the evaluated cement plant dataset, the most important features for strength prediction include LOI and various proxies for particle sizes. A cautious interpretation of these correlations suggests variable limestone content as well as over- and under-grinding as the main sources of strength variability, in contrast to a relatively well-optimized clinker. Overall, this case study demonstrates how interpretable Machine Learning can give key insights for monitoring and optimization of LC3 quality in production.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Limestone-calcined clay cement, Explainable Artificial Intelligence

1 Introduction

LC3 comprises an eco-efficient blend of pozzolanic component (calcined clay), filler component (limestone), and clinker with gypsum. A typical LC3-X blend can be described as X% clinker, 5% gypsum, and a supplementary mix of limestone and calcined clay (LC2) in a 1:2 ratio; with LC3-50 and LC3-65 being the most common blends.

Performance of a cement blend is evaluated through various properties – with durability and compressive strength (CS) being the most commonly used metrics to compare LC3 to Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), when evaluated against existing quality standards (EN-197-1, ASTM C109). LC3-50 develops lower CS than OPC during the initial curing intervals (1, 3, and 7 days). However, by 28 days, its performance

converges with that of OPC, and at extended curing ages LC3 typically surpasses OPC [11]. In this work, we focus on the compressive strength of LC3 at 28 days, as it is a comparable standard strength quality assessment in cement plants across cement types.

In cement production, practical limitations regarding scalable implementation of new material streams become apparent. For LC3, a key practical question is whether to blend the LC2 with OPC or co-grinding the limestone, calcined clay, gypsum and clinker. Studies in this field have reported that co-grinding clinker with limestone and calcined clay leads to lower performing blends [4]. This is attributed to the over-grinding of the limestone and calcined clay, while undergrinding the clinker components. Clinker, being considerably harder, gets coated by fine particles of limestone and calcined clay, lowering the overall grinding efficiency [12]. Poorly ground clinker then fails to hydrate sufficiently to provide optimum strength. In addition, over-grinding of limestone and calcined clay is likely to increase water demand of the blend, making the material hard to work with in concrete production. Besides, granulation of the ultra-fine components can occur; and this can lead to poor blending with the clinker.

The clinker, limestone, calcined clay and gypsum are distinguishable by their chemical composition; and chemical composition within one material is related to the mineralogical composition and thus strength development. This is why we expect CS to be correlated to the chemical composition of LC3 and hence informative to Machine Learning models.

Machine Learning (ML), with its ability to uncover non-linear correlations from data, has been applied extensively in cement and concrete research, including predictions of CS, setting time, or rheology. However, the current literature appears to overestimate the capabilities of ML models for CS predictions, where data leakage and improper train-test splits are among the causes and common pitfalls [8]. Previously, CS of cement paste has been successfully predicted from chemical and physical properties on datasets from literature reviews for OPC [10] and calcium sulfoaluminate cement [7]. For OPC, a case study also demonstrated CS predictability by ML models in production [6].

Correlations in production datasets are conceptually different from literature or laboratory datasets. Laboratory data typically aims to explore a wide range of compositions from the same material source, whereas literature data implicitly refers to materials from different cement plants. In contrast, production data from a single cement plant faces variations in raw materials and operating conditions over time, while trying to minimize variance of product quality. This causes different correlation structures and scales of variability in these dataset types; and one cannot conclude that ML is applicable in production from a successful use case on literature or laboratory data.

The research on ML for CS prediction of LC3 has so far focused on the optimization of its material composition, i.e. the ratios of clinker, limestone and calcined clay; with successful applications on datasets from literature reviews [5, 3, 9] and laboratory data [1]. To the best of our knowledge, this work is the first paper to address Machine Learning for compressive strength prediction of limestone-calcined clay cement in a production environment. We report a 26-31% reduction in various prediction errors of our models compared to the production mean, and demonstrate how to gain actionable

insights from model explanations, carefully taking into account the difference of correlation and causation.

2 Data and Materials

The dataset in this study covers 17 months of production data from one cement plant producing various cement types in several mills. The LC3 is commercially available and classified as Cement Type UG (Use General) according to NTC 121. This cement type is comparable to ASTM C1157 (Type GU) in application and has a minimum 28-day CS of 24.0 MPa. The cement CS at different ages as well as its chemical and physical properties are recorded daily. These include the chemical composition measured by x-ray fluorescence, specific surface area by the Blaine test, Retained sieve no. 325 (45 μ m), set point percentage of LC2, water demand and flow (ASTM C1437-20). The cement investigated in this study refers to co-grinded LC3.

3 Essentials of Machine Learning

Supervised Machine Learning aims at learning an input-to-output map based on available input-output pairs, the data. This map is a statistical model, whose parameters are trained by minimizing the resulting prediction error. ML models can be generally complex with many parameters, and too complex models can memorize the dataset. Therefore, ML models need to be evaluated on unseen data, to determine how well they generalize. This is usually done by splitting the dataset in two disjoint sets: the training set, where the model is fitted, and the test set, where the model's performance is evaluated. There are different methods for a train-test-split. Albeit it is common practice to split the data randomly, this is not accurate for a production environment; specifically, due to auto-correlation and temporal hidden confounders, e.g. similar raw material properties and plant conditions at nearby times, it is more appropriate to implement a timeseries split. In that case, the known data until a split time is treated as the training set, and the data afterwards as the test set. This effectively simulates how a model would have performed if it had been trained at the split time. Note that the 28-day CS of cement can only be known for cement that was produced at least 28 days before, which introduces a necessary lag of 28 days between training and test sets. When ML models are deployed, it is good practice to re-train models regularly on new data to obtain the best possible predictions. An example of this procedure is visualised in Fig. 1b.

Metrics are used to evaluate model performance. They assign one score (to be maximized) or error (to be minimized) to the whole set of predictions. Common metrics for regression tasks include the mean absolute error (MAE), root mean squared error (RMSE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and maximum error (MAX). Their definitions are given in Table 1. MAE, RMSE and MAX are in the unit of the target, whereas the MAPE is in percent. Metrics are not comparable across different datasets, which is why it is useful to compare ML models to a baseline prediction without ML.

Table 1. Definition of common regression metrics. The prediction is denoted as \hat{y} and the true value as y .

Name	Definition	Name	Definition
MAE	$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \hat{y}_i - y_i $	MAPE	$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left \frac{\hat{y}_i - y_i}{y_i} \right $
RMSE	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}$	MAX	$\max_i \hat{y}_i - y_i $

Models: Tree ensembles are ML models that consist of decision trees. Each tree is fitted to a bootstrapped subset of the data, and the tree predictions are aggregated over all trees in the ensemble (forest). At each node of a tree, a split feature and a split value are selected. The data is then divided in two partitions; namely the samples that have the split feature smaller than the split value and those samples that do not. For each child node, this split procedure is repeated with a new split feature and split value, until either a maximum number of splits is reached, the maximum depth, or the data in a child can no longer be separated. This yields a hierarchical model, the decision tree, where the final children are called leaves. Each leaf is associated to one value, which is the mean of the training samples in that leaf. At inference, the sample traverses the tree by testing whether its split features are below or above the split values of the tree, which identifies the test sample's leaf and its associated prediction. The most widely used tree ensembles are RandomForests, which optimize both the split feature and the split value at each step. A variation thereof is the ExtraTrees model, which selects the split feature randomly and only optimizes the split value. The number of trees in an ensemble as well as the maximum depth of each tree are hyperparameters, which need to be chosen before the model is fitted. Figure 1a depicts the concept of tree ensembles.

Fig. 1. a) Concept of Tree Ensembles. b) 4-fold timeseries train-test split with one month gap and one month forecast horizon.

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) algorithms can identify how the model came to a certain prediction and which features played a role. The concept of explaining is not trivially defined and there is a myriad of concepts related to explainability [2]. Local feature importance refers to an explanation of a single sample, whereas global feature importance explains what in general influences the model’s prediction. There are model-agnostic explainers, though models based on decision trees are intrinsically explainable: The prediction difference from the parent node to the child node can be directly attributed to the split feature. Importantly, model interpretability explains what the model looks at to predict the target, which can be interpreted as a non-linear correlation. However, correlation is not causation and feature importance should not be misinterpreted as causal strength.

4 Experiments and Results

All experiments were conducted with the scikit-learn library in Python. We train an `ExtraTreesRegressor` with 500 trees and a maximum depth of 15 splits in a pipeline with a `MinMaxScaler`. The maximum depth is chosen slightly higher than the number of features to ensure that, on average, all features are considered; while the high number of trees ensures robustness of both predictions and feature importance. The `ExtraTrees` feature importance is more robust than a `RandomForest` in case of correlated features due to the random selection of the split feature, i.e. correlated features share the importance. A preliminary comparison to other models and hyperparameters revealed no significant change in predictive performance; however, a full analysis on model selection and hyperparameter optimization is beyond the scope of this paper.

We carried out a timeseries split with monthly re-training on the data of the last twelve available months and predicted 28-day CS with a time lag of one month to account for the intrinsic curing delay of 28 days. To provide a baseline for comparison, we chose the average over the training set as a prediction for every test sample, simulating the optimal prediction without considering any cement features. The timeseries split with the exact split ratios is shown in Fig. 1b, and the results on the test sets with predictions and metrics are shown in Fig. 2a, with a feature importance analysis in Fig. 2b. Test metrics for the ML model and the baseline are also reported in Table 2.

Overall, Fig. 2a shows that the predictions follow the measurements well. At times, the model is able to almost perfectly predict CS (e.g. fold 4), whereas for other periods (e.g. samples 20-25) the model does not appear to improve the baseline prediction. All ML prediction errors are smaller than the baseline errors, with a reduction of 26-31%, as shown in Table 2.

Fig. 2. a) Predictions of strength and metrics of the ML models on the test sets. The shaded area indicates the plant measurement error. Due to small sample size, we evaluate metrics across all folds. b) Feature Importance. The red line indicates the average feature importance as a threshold.

Based on Fig. 2b, the single most important feature with around 30% contribution is the LOI of the cement. Furthermore, CaO, Alkali equivalent and particle size (Blaine, Retained no. 325, water demand) play a secondary role, whereas the other features appear less important. The importance of other main oxides, such as SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, as well as Free Lime is much lower than the average expected importance, indicating that variability in clinker quality does not contribute to the model's prediction - which does not imply that clinker does not contribute to strength. Furthermore, the SO₃, which is mainly governed by gypsum, exhibits a low feature importance, as does surprisingly the ratio of the LC2.

Table 2. Metrics on the joint test set.

Metric	RMSE	MAE	MAX	MAPE
Unit	MPa	MPa	MPa	%
Baseline	2.19	1.80	5.48	6.41
ML	1.61	1.28	3.77	4.54
Reduction	26%	29%	31%	29%

5 Discussion

It is well-documented that LC3 quality in a co-grinding setting is more challenging to control than in separate grinding [13]. Variations in hardness, quartz content, moisture and general material variability render an optimal operation of the mill difficult, which in turn can lead to fluctuations in cement quality. Although this variation is not desirable, it enables the use of ML models that can predict variability in CS from variations in chemical composition and particle size. In fact, our ML model for CS predictions is 26-31% better than the uninformative baseline, depending on the metric.

To gain actionable insights from the feature importance, it is paramount to understand that ML models consider correlations and that correlations are not causation. Besides, ML models predict variability of the output from input variability, which implies that unimportant features can be either due to small feature variability, or a lack of correlation with the target. In this light, the XAI results help identify optimization potential.

For the presented case study, the high importance of the LOI as a limestone proxy together with the relatively low importance of LC2 ratio in Fig. 2b suggest that the limestone content within the LC2 varies, which could be optimized in the future. In contrast, the negligible importance of features such as Free Lime and main clinker oxides (Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2) indicates a low variability in clinker quality, and hence an already close-to-optimal clinker line. Particle size and water demand for ultra-fines fraction, both important for strength predictions, are to a greater extent linked to the mill operation and the known trade-off in overgrinding soft materials and under-grinding hard ones.

While 28-day CS is not the only cement quality parameter prescribed by standards, the production cost also plays an important role, especially in decision-making for process control, e.g. throughput and quality optimization in cement mill operation. A quantitative estimate of CS with ML before the 28 curing days necessary for laboratory results can aid in this adversarial optimization problem, and it could be an important pillar in a future performance-based market.

6 Conclusions

In this case study, we use Machine Learning to predict 28-day Compressive Strength of co-grinded LC3 in production. We report an improvement in strength predictions of 26-31% w.r.t. a no-ML baseline. Besides, XAI techniques reveal a high feature importance of LOI and particle size information, which suggests that our model correctly captures the importance of limestone and the trade-off between over- and under-grinding for co-grinded LC3. Furthermore, we conclude from the low feature importance of clinker features, that the clinker quality is stable and the sources of strength fluctuations likely stem from milling conditions and variability in LC2 composition. To conclude, our paper presents the first case study on how explainable ML can support a process expert to take informed decisions in monitoring and optimizing LC3 production.

Acknowledgments. The authors would like to acknowledge the support from the project “Data Enabling Transformation and Optimization towards Concrete Sustainability” (DETOCS) that is funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101119929. Funded by the European Union - views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.

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PRE-PRINT PEER REVIEWED